

The Academy of
Business in Society

EABIS Research 2002-2012

Business in Society
&
Corporate Responsibility

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**Business in Society
&
Corporate Responsibility**

EABIS Research

2002-2012

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For more information on EABIS members and core activities:

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On Business in Society and Corporate Responsibility

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Introduction

We are pleased to present to you EABIS' latest publication – a comprehensive overview of the range of research-based outputs generated through our projects in the past ten years.

Building upon the work of the talented scholars within our network, this report highlights the diversity of themes being addressed by our member institutions. This overview serves also to underline the deep and unwavering commitment of EABIS to cutting-edge knowledge development and learning on the changing role of business in society.

We hope that readers get a clear sense of the volume of knowledge and insight developed across 24 different initiatives – which have received invaluable support from our Corporate Founding Partners and the European Commission. Since the creation of EABIS, corporate responsibility issues have moved to the forefront of organisational agendas worldwide. Research has a critical role to play in re-shaping current practice and theory – within corporations, governments and key stakeholder organisations.

Against a backdrop of increasing complexity and societal expectation, there has never been a more urgent need and demand for robust, practical knowledge that can support companies in adapting to the new realities of doing business.

With its unique collaborative model of business – academic partnership, EABIS members and its secretariat have contributed more than 100 internal and external outputs from research. These include peer-reviewed journals, papers, cases, and other published articles, as well as the growing series of EABIS branded books.

These materials – taken together with over 750 submissions of corporate responsibility-related, research-based inputs at our Annual Colloquia (2003 to 2011) – underline EABIS' importance as a dynamic reference point for an international community of research scholars and stakeholders.

Yours truly,

Dr. David Bevan
Director, Academic Affairs

Simon Pickard
Director General

Bottom of the Pyramid (B.O.P)

EABIS Research Project

Title: A New Paradigm for the "Bottom of the Pyramid":
Corporate - Entrepreneurship Partnerships to Develop
Customers, Markets & Portfolios

Executive Summary: This research project examined the potential synergies between those entrepreneurs and companies willing to create new markets that are distinct from their current customer bases. This was viewed as a novel way of looking at corporate renewal and innovation enacted on the fringes of the market system. More specifically, it aimed to:

- Understand and characterize innovative entrepreneurial organisations in underdeveloped markets
- Characterize and assess their role in the sustainable development agenda
- Model those organisations from a resource-based view as partners and competitors of corporations in global markets.

Budget: € 31.500

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: March 2005 to March 2006

Lead Partner(s): IESE Business School

Supporting Partner(s): N/A

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): See below

Research Papers:

Seelos, C., Mair, J. (2005a). *Sustainable development, sustainable profit*. European Business Forum, Vol. 20, pp.49-53.

Seelos, C., Ganly, K. & Mair, J. (2006). *Social entrepreneurs directly contribute to global development goals*. Published in Mair, J., Robinson, J. and Hockerts, K. (Eds), *Social Entrepreneurship*. Palgrave Macmillan., Part 4, 235-275.

Mair, J. & Seelos, C. (2006). *The Sekem Initiative: a holistic vision to develop people*. In *New Social Entrepreneurship*:

What awaits social entrepreneurship ventures? F. Perrini (Ed.), Edgar Elgar.

Seelos, C. & Mair, J. (2006). *How social entrepreneurs enable human, social, and economic development*. In Harvard Business School (Ed.), *Alleviating Global Poverty*. Jossey-Bass: San Francisco, CA.

Mair, J. & Martí, I. (2008). *Entrepreneurship in and around institutional voids: A case study from Bangladesh*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 24(5): 419-435.

Seelos, C. & Mair, J. (2005). *Hope for sustainable development: Social entrepreneurs make it happen*. IESE Paper: D-611-E, October 2005. Under review at *Business & Society*.

Mair, J. & Schoen, O. (2005). *Social entrepreneurial business models in the context of developing economies: An exploratory study*. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 2(1): 54-68.

Research Cases:

Seelos, C. & Mair, J. (2006). *BRAC: An enabling structure for social and economic development*. IESE Study 34.

Thurner, C., Seelos, C. & Mair, J. (2006). *Wasteconcern*. IESE Study 33.

Business Case for Corporate Responsibility

EABIS Research Project

Title: Measurement of Corporate Responsibility: Linking Financial and Social Performance and Value

Executive Summary: This research project sought to understand how firms trade off investment between social and financial objectives and how firms decide between projects with competing social objectives. Key objectives were to:

- Develop a rigorous model for firms to make business decisions that identify the value to the firm and its source, as well as articulate the value to society
- Develop a managerially-focused model as well as a measurement approach that sets out the sources and amount of social capital and stakeholder value that are recognised by social partners

- Articulate a business in society-focused framework that expresses a new case for a globalised knowledge economy.

Budget: € 60.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: April 2005 to March 2007

Lead Partner(s): Cranfield School of Management

Supporting Partner(s): Henley Management College, SDA Bocconi, Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School, University of Applied Sciences in Business and Administration, Zurich (HWZ).

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): Moir, L. & Kennerley, M. (2006). *What to Measure in the 21st Century*. Book chapter contribution to *CSR – Reconciling Aspiration with Application* (Kakabadse, A. & Morsing, M.). Palgrave MacMillan.

Moir, L. (2006). *Corporate Responsibility: Measuring the Business Benefits*. Ethical Corporation Magazine, July Issue.

Ferguson, D. (2008). *A Business Practitioner's Guide for Measuring Corporate Responsibility*. Doughty Centre Occasional Paper, Cranfield University School of Management.

EABIS Branded Book

Title: **Business of Sustainability**

Author(s) / Editor(s): Ulrich Steger, IMD

Publisher: Palgrave Macmillan

Date of Publication: May 2004

Summary: The contents of the book explore the economic rationale for corporate sustainability by approaching the issue on an industry-specific level. The result of an extensive empirical evidence gathered from managers in nine industries, along with their stakeholders, the book gives a detailed and representative insight of the business case in the sectors as well as a unique cross-industry perspective on the issue.

Title: **CSR – Reconciling Aspiration with Application**

Author(s) / Editor(s): Andrew Kakabadse (Cranfield) and Mette Morsing (Copenhagen)

Publisher: Palgrave Macmillan

Date of Publication: January 2006

Summary: This book features a collection of articles from leading academics, NGOs, researchers and businesses across Europe that examine the key questions and issues in corporate responsibility including governance, practical reporting tools, the challenges facing business schools and integrating corporate responsibility into business practices.

Climate Change

Title: **International Business and Global Climate Change**

Author(s) / Editor(s): Jonatan Pinkse and Ans Kolk, University of Amsterdam

Publisher: Routledge

Date of Publication: March 2009

Summary: Climate change has become an important topic on the business agenda with strong pressure being placed on companies to respond and contribute to finding solutions to this urgent problem. This book provides a comprehensive analysis of international business responses to global climate change and climate change as well as a concise treatment of developments in policy and business activity on global, regional and national levels, using examples and systematic data from a large number of international companies.

Competitiveness

Title: **Corporate Responsibility, Competitiveness and Human / Social Capital**

Guest Editor(s): Lenssen, G., Gasparski, W., Rok, B. & Lacy, P.

Journal Issue: *Corporate Governance, the International Journal of Business in Society*, Volume 6, number 4

Publisher: Emerald Insight

Date of Publication: September 2006

Table of Contents: **Corporate responsibility and competitiveness at the macro level**

Zadek, S. *Responsible competitiveness: reshaping global markets through responsible business practices*

Rodrigues, M.J. *The Lisbon Strategy after the mid-term review: implications for innovation and life-long learning*

Eberhard-Harribey, L. *Corporate social responsibility as a new paradigm in the European policy: how CSR comes to legitimate the European regulation process*

Midttun, A., Gautesen, K. & Gjølborg, M. *The political economy of CSR in Western Europe*

Albareda, L., Tencati, A., Lozano, J.M. & Perrini, F. *The government's role in promoting corporate responsibility: a comparative analysis of Italy and UK from the relational state perspective*

Bonfiglioli, E., Moir, L. & Ambrosini, V. *Developing the wider role of business in society: the experience of Microsoft in developing training and supporting employability*

Corporate responsibility and competitiveness at the meso level

Draper, S. *Key models for delivering sector-level corporate responsibility*

Senge, P., Dow, M. & Neath, G. *Learning together: new partnerships for new times*

Agyeman-Budu, E.A. & Welvaert, F. *Investing in health care management: a way to explore the future value outlook of the health care sector*

Lewicka-Strzalecka, A. *Opportunities and limitations of CSR in the postcommunist countries: the Polish case*

Lerberg Jorgensen, A. & Steen Knudsen, J. *Sustainable competitiveness in global value chains: how do small Danish firms behave?*

Sobczak, A., Debucquet, G. & Havard, C. *The impact of higher education on students' and young managers' perception of companies and CSR: an exploratory analysis*

Responsible competitiveness at the “micro” level of the firm

Ayuso, S., Rodríguez, M.A. & Ricart, J.E. *Using stakeholder dialogue as a source for new ideas: a dynamic capability underlying sustainable innovation*

de Wit, M., Wade, M. & Schouten, E. *Hardwiring and softwiring corporate responsibility: a vital combination*

Sachs, S., Maurer, M., Rühli E. & Hoffmann, R. *Corporate social responsibility from a “stakeholder view” perspective: CSR implementation by a Swiss mobile telecommunication provider*

Molteni, M. *The social-competitive innovation pyramid*

Clarke, M. & Butcher, D. *Voluntarism as an organizing principle for “responsible organizations”*

Consumer Behaviour and Marketing

EABIS Research Project

Title: **Consumer Perceptions of Corporate Responsibility**
Activities: Consumer Attributions and the Halo Effect

Executive Summary: This project is constructed around a series of studies to test the posited attributions and, more specifically, the halo effect on consumers' perceptions of company CR practices and motives. The research proposes examining in multiple studies both social and environmental initiatives, in the form of actions on climate change and in activities that address the needs of the base of the pyramid (BOP). Key dependent variables are brand and consumer reputation.

The project comprises four major parts, each of approximately three to six months. First, there would be a period of theory development and formulation of hypotheses. Second, the development and pilot testing of scenarios describing hypothetical company climate change and BOP initiatives and our dependent measures. Third, analysis of our main studies and write-up of our research findings.

Budget: € 61.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme
Period: 18 months
Lead Partner(s): INSEAD Social Innovation Centre / INSEAD
Supporting Partner(s): Durham Business School
Internal Report(s): N/A to date
External Publication(s): N/A to date

The intended deliverables of this project are a report for EABIS members and broader dissemination, an article for an appropriate scholarly international journal (e.g., *Journal of Consumer Research* or *Journal of Consumer Psychology*) and an article for a suitable managerial journal (e.g., *California Management Review* or *Sloan Management Review*), in addition to related working paper(s) and presentation at academic conference(s).

Diversity

EU Research Project

Title: **The Business Case for Diversity**

Executive Summary: In 2005, the European Commission, Directorate General Employment, Social Affairs & Equal Opportunities commissioned a study entitled “The Business Case for Diversity – Good Practices in the Workplace.” The aim of the study was to promote the development of diversity policies in companies by examining perceived business benefits, challenges and examples of good practices.

In 2006, it was decided to undertake a follow-up study that would extend the research to small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and intermediary organisations. As part of this new work, the Commission also called for a focused study of the current activities and potential role of European business schools in equipping current and future business leaders and managers with the skills and competencies to manage diversity in the workplace.

Within these parameters, an EABIS consortium examined the “state of the art” in research, teaching, student affairs and institutional policy. On the back of the data and insights generated, an exploration was also conducted on the feasibility of creating a network of business schools and companies to

support further collaboration and knowledge development on the subject of diversity management.

Budget: € 980.000

Funding Source: DG Employment & Social Affairs, European Commission

Period: January 2008 to December 2008

Lead Partner(s): Focus Consultancy UK, EABIS, EIM, EIMD

Supporting Partner(s): UEAPME, CSR Europe, European Foundation for Management Development (EFMD), European Business Test Panel (DG MARKET), Austrian Institute for SME Research

Internal Report(s): Rahbek Pedersen, E., Tywuschik, S. & Sanchez Gardey, G. (2008). *Diversity Management in Business Schools: Emerging Trends, New Priorities & Good Practices*.

Focus Consultancy & EIM (2008). *Diversity for Talent and Competitiveness: the SME Business Case for Diversity*.

Focus Consultancy (2008). *Diversity Management in 2008: Research with the European Business Test Panel*.

Focus Consulting (2008). *Diversity and Innovation: A Business Opportunity for All*.

Focus Consulting (2008). *Voluntary Diversity Initiatives in and for Europe: the Role of Diversity Charters*.

External Publication(s): EABIS, Focus Consulting, EIMD, EIM (2008). *Continuing the Diversity Journey – Business Practices, Perspectives and Benefits*. A Consortium Report to the European Commission (DG EMPL)

Rahbek Pedersen, E. *Diversity Management at Business Schools and Universities: - How Do We Change Tomorrow's Managers?* Article for book based on ESSEC conference papers, April 2009.

Economics

EABIS Research Project

Title: Economy and Society: The Future of Economics and Management in a Post-Crisis World

Executive Summary: This initiative seeks to convene a forward-looking, balanced, reflective and informed debate, including academics and practitioners, to connect macro-economic perspectives with

corporate governance, corporate strategy and management. This integrative debate has so far not taken place. The following critical points requiring urgent reflection have emerged from recent high-level discussion among EABIS members:

How significant is the current crisis for economics? This question has given rise to a polarised debate between those who believe the crisis is consistent with standard economic principles and those who see it as wholly inconsistent. Unresolved issues include which lessons need to be learned for the future of economics, for the role of finance in the economy and in society, for the management of the global economy and the role of institutions of governance, all of which must also be considered from a longer-term historical perspective.

Must we abandon the equilibrium-based paradigm of economics? Some argue that “economics is broken” because of its failure to anticipate past and current developments and its misleading conclusions that follow from its assumptions – i.e., that market-based competition brings the best outcomes even when market failure and imperfections are rife. Others argue that the demise of the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) in financial economics does not mean that the whole of economics (involving its many branches and sub-fields) is “broken”. Also, institutional economics and behavioural economics are gaining recognition and legitimacy. What is their contribution?

Economics is a core discipline in the business curriculum. It is central to the analysis of markets, it feeds into finance and it informs the teaching of other subjects such as international business, strategic management and corporate governance. Yet its long-standing focus on perfect information, market efficiency and rational choice is often at odds with the reality of modern management. Should economics remain at the heart of the business curriculum given what many now regard as its unrealistic assumptions about human nature? Or its inherently cynical views on human nature which has taken self-fulfilling powers? If economics is to retain its core position, how should economics be taught – as a set of ideas, a system of analysis, a set of beliefs, a practical philosophy (as it was originally conceived)?

How should economics and management incorporate issues of global sustainability and global governance? How should major social, environmental and governance pressures that increasingly affect markets, companies, regulators and consumers be addressed? What is the relationship between economics, management and governance? What constitutes sustained comparative advantage in the global economy? What is the balance

between competition and collaboration? Can collaborative governance models be effective in enhancing sustainability of global markets?

What does all this mean for strategy and management?

There is **substantially increased systemic complexity and potential turbulence** in global economic systems. This may call for different models and approaches to managerial economics and strategic management. This may also question the relevance of firm-centric approaches like agency theory and stakeholder theory. Ultimately, our challenge is to understand how economics will help managers to make better decisions in a post crisis era and how students of business and management can be better prepared for this world.

Budget: € 10.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: April 2010

Lead Partner(s): Catholic University of Milan, EABIS

Supporting Partner(s): Fondazione ISTUD, Bocconi University, Solvay Business School, INSEAD, EFMD

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): A Special Issue of the *Journal of Management Development* (forthcoming 2011). Emerald Insight Publishing.

Education & Curriculum Development

EABIS Research Project

Title: Curriculum Development for Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility

Executive Summary: This project focused on leveraging new business-academic partnerships to develop mainstream teaching materials that could be used to mainstream corporate responsibility into all management disciplines as well as case ethics and corporate responsibility courses. It involved both academic and corporate members of EABIS in a collaborative exercise to promote, create, review and analyse case-writing innovation.

Budget: € 350.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: March 2005 - May 2009

Lead Partner(s): INSEAD. London Business School

Supporting Partner(s): IESE Business School, SDA Bocconi School of Management, INSEAD, IMD, China European International Business School (CEIBS), Copenhagen Business School, Cranfield University School of Management, Catholic University Eichstaett-Ingolstadt, Oxfam.

Corporate Partner(s): IBM, Johnson & Johnson, Microsoft, Shell, Unilever, Innocent, illycaffè, betapharm, Novo Nordisk, Iberdrola, Enel, Wasteconcern, Norsk Hydro,

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): Smith, N.C. & Lenssen, G. (2009), *Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility*

(See below for details)

Collaborative development of 13 case studies for use in mainstream management curricula and training courses:

1. Norsk Hydro ASA: Sustainable PVC at Hydro Polymers? (INSEAD)
2. Waste Concern: Turning a Problem into a Resource (IESE)
3. Enel: CSR and Performance Measurement (Bocconi)
4. IBERDROLA: A Utility's Approach to Sustainability and Stakeholder Management (IESE)
5. illycaffè: Value Creation through Responsible Supplier Relationships (Bocconi)
6. Innocent: Values and Value (Cranfield)
7. betapharm: Be Different or Die (Eichstätt-Ingolstadt)
8. Unilever and Oxfam: Understanding the Impacts of Business on Poverty (INSEAD)
9. Microsoft: Bringing Technology to the Aging Population (Bocconi)
10. Revenue Flow and Human Rights: A Paradox for Shell Nigeria (IMD)
11. IBM China: Responding to a Government's Social Initiatives & IBM China: Designing a Stakeholder Assessment Team (CEIBS)

12. Novo Nordisk A/S – Integrating Sustainability into Business Practice (CBS)

EABIS Branded Book

Title: **Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility**

Author(s) / Editor(s): N. Craig Smith, INSEAD and Gilbert Lenssen, EABIS

Publisher: John Wiley and Sons Ltd

Date of Publication: June 2009

Summary: Corporate Responsibility (CR) has never been more prominent on the corporate agenda. More companies are coming to understand that it is in their economic interest to address social and environmental impacts in a manner that is integrated with their operations. CR encompasses issues such as sustainability (meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs), stakeholder management, and corporate governance, as well as corporate philanthropy.

Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility takes an innovative approach to CR. Based around case studies commissioned by EABIS, the book is structured around major subject areas in the business school curriculum. It provides a chapter on the relevance of CR to each subject area and identifies CR issues to be addressed.

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Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility
N. Craig Smith, INSEAD, and Gilbert Lenssen, EABIS

Business as Usual is Not the Answer to Society's Problems
N. Craig Smith, INSEAD, and Halina Ward, IIED

Strategy

Corporate Responsibility in Strategy
Andrew M. Pettigrew, Saïd Business School, University of Oxford

Microsoft: Bringing Technology to the Aging Population
Maurizio Zollo, Bocconi University and Robert J. Crawford, INSEAD

IBM in China: Responding to a Government's Social Initiatives
Steven White, CEIBS

IBERDROLA: A Utility's Approach to Sustainability and Stakeholder Management

Tanguy Jacopin, IESE Business School, Serge Poisson-de Haro, HEC Montreal and Joan Fontrodona, IESE Business School

Accounting

Corporate Responsibility in Accounting

Dennis Oswald, University of Michigan

Enel: CSR and Performance Measurement

Anna Pistoni and Lucrezia Songini, Bocconi University

Novo Nordisk A/S – Integrating Sustainability into Business Practice

Mette Morsing, Copenhagen Business School and Dennis Oswald, University of Michigan

Finance

From Grace to Disgrace: The Rise and Fall of Arthur Andersen

N. Craig Smith, INSEAD and Michelle Quirk, London Business School

Corporate Social Responsibility in Finance

John Becker-Blease, Washington State University

Maximizing Shareholders Value: An Ethical Responsibility?

Theo Vermaelen, INSEAD

Veridian: Putting a Value on Values

Rakesh Khurana, Joel Podolny and Jaan Elias, Harvard Business School

Economics

Corporate Responsibility in Economics

H. Landis Gabel, INSEAD

Unilever and Oxfam: Understanding the Impacts of Business on Poverty

N. Craig Smith, INSEAD and Robert J. Crawford, London Business School

Revenue Flow and Human Rights: A Paradox for Shell Nigeria

Ulrich Steger and Aileen Ionescu-Somers, IMD

Entrepreneurship

Corporate Responsibility in Entrepreneurship

Filipe Santos, INSEAD

innocent: Values and Value

David Grayson and Robert Brown, Cranfield School of Management

Waste Concern: Turning a Problem into a Resource

Johanna Mair and Jordan Mitchell, IESE Business School

Marketing

Corporate Responsibility in Marketing

C.B. Bhattacharya, Boston University and Sankar Sen, Baruch College, City University of New York

Bounded Goodness: Marketing Implications of Drucker on Corporate Responsibility

N. Craig Smith, INSEAD

Norsk Hydro ASA: Sustainable PVC at Hydro Polymers?

N. Craig Smith, INSEAD and Josephine Brennan, London Business School

GlaxoSmithKline and Access to Essential Medicines

N. Craig Smith, INSEAD and Anne Duncan, London Business School

Organisational Behaviour and Human Resource Management

Corporate Responsibility in Organizational Behaviour

Mette Morsing, Copenhagen Business School

betapharm: Be Different or Die

Andre Habisch and Stefan Kaiser, Eichstätt-Ingolstadt School of Management and Nigel Roome, RSM Erasmus University

The TPG-WFP Partnership: Looking for a Partner

Luk N. Van Wassenhove and Rolando M. Tomasini, INSEAD

Operations Management

Corporate Responsibility in Operations Management

Luk N. Van Wassenhove, INSEAD

illycaffè: Value Creation Through Responsible Supplier Relationships

Francesco Perrini, Bocconi University and Angeloantonio Russo, Parthenope University

The Co-operative Group: Fair trade Chocolate

Adrian Clarke, Josephine Brennan, Stephanie Robertson and Chris Voss, London Business School

The Wal-Mart Supply Chain Controversy

N. Craig Smith, INSEAD and Robert J. Crawford, London Business School

Editor Peer-Reviewed Special Issue Journal

Title:	Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility
Guest Editor(s):	Smith, N.C. & Lenssen, G.
Journal Issue:	Journal of Business Ethics Education, Volume 5
Publisher:	Neilson Journals
Date of Publication:	September 2008
Table of Contents:	Unilever and Oxfam: Understanding the Impacts of Business on Poverty (A) and (B) <i>N. Craig Smith and Robert J. Crawford</i>
	IBERDROLA: A Utility's Approach to Sustainability and Stakeholder Management <i>Tanguy Jacopin, Joan Fontrodona and Serge Poisson-de Haro</i>
	illycaffè: Value Creation through Responsible Supplier Relationships <i>Francesco Perrini and Angeloantonio Russo</i>
	Innocent: Values and Value <i>Robert Brown and David Grayson</i>
	Novo Nordisk A/S: Integrating Sustainability into Business Practice <i>Mette Morsing and Dennis Oswald</i>
	Waste Concern: Turning a Problem into Resource <i>Johanna Mair and Jordan Mitchell</i>
	Revenue Flow and Human Rights: A Paradox for Shell Nigeria <i>Aileen Ionescu-Somers and Ulrich Steger</i>

EABIS Research Project

Title:	Innovative Pedagogies for Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility
Executive Summary:	The assignment for this project was formulated as: "Investigate various alternative pedagogies that business schools, companies and other organisations can and are using, to teach CR and explore how they might be brought into the mainstream of business and management learning".

The research team therefore set out to identify and examine the best innovative teaching initiatives, both within a university environment as well as within companies/in-house management training, with a view to knowledge-sharing (inspiration) between universities and companies.

Budget: € 55.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: July 2009 to January 2012

Lead Partner(s): Copenhagen Business School, Nottingham University Business School (ICCSR)

Supporting Partner(s): ESADE Business School, INSEAD, IBM, Microsoft, Shell

Internal Report(s): Murphy, R. & Sharma, M. (2009). *Literature Review on Innovative Pedagogies for Curriculum Mainstreaming*.

Pedersen, K. (2009). *Curriculum Development and Innovative Pedagogies*. Final Project Report.

External Publication(s): N/A to date.

EABIS Research Project

Title: Mainstreaming CR through Executive Education

Executive Summary: Economic conditions have focused line managers' attention almost exclusively on operational functioning and efficiency. This makes the CR or Sustainability Managers' job harder than ever, because to fully succeed he or she needs to coordinate with line managers and integrate CR into business processes.

Executive Education providers can be key partners in companies' efforts to mainstream CR; of course, they need to be keenly aware of line managers' needs and pressures in order to be effective.

We have designed this workshop as a small, informal yet structured forum in which representatives from both the supply and demand side of the Executive Education equation can share innovation, ideas, experience and information, and promote knowledge on the following crucial elements:

- the link between sustainability, decisional process and managerial action;
- the competencies and skills needed to support this changing cultural process;

- the problems deriving from multi-national dimensions when linking organisational transformation to the change agency role of individual managers;
- the importance of a systemic view on sustainability and the different ways of its operationalisation;
- new modalities for learning (experiential/action/content);
- the role of executive education and training programmes

Budget: € 10.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: Autumn 2009 to April 2010

Lead Partner(s): Fondazione ISTUD

Supporting Partner(s): EABIS, IBM, ENI Corporate University, IMD, Ashridge

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): N/A to date

EABIS Education Conference Outputs

Title: EABIS European Education & Training Exchanges on Corporate Responsibility

Executive Summary: From 2005 to 2007, EABIS – with the generous support of Corporate Founding Partner Johnson & Johnson – staged an annual forum during its Colloquium, specifically to balance its traditional support for research with efforts on education and training.

The aim of the Education & Training Exchanges was to build a platform to showcase and discuss best practice on integrating the role of business in society into the mainstream of management learning and development. A key objective throughout was to bridge the gap between business and academia, enabling the sharing of new ideas, mutual learning and success stories.

The Exchange rapidly became one of the most dynamic platforms for dialogue between corporate managers and executive education providers. In three years, almost 200 case studies and initiatives from around the world were presented and discussed. On each occasion, a Catalogue of Initiatives captured the essence of these for future dissemination.

Budget: € 18.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: September 2005 – September 2007

Lead Partner(s): EABIS, Johnson & Johnson

Supporting Partner(s): Leon Kozminski Academy of Entrepreneurship and Management, (LKAEM), SDA Bocconi School of Management, ESADE Business School

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): European Corporate Responsibility Education & Training Exchange: Catalogue of Initiatives (2005)

European Corporate Responsibility Education & Training Exchange: Catalogue of Initiatives (2006)

European Corporate Responsibility Education & Training Exchange: Catalogue of Initiatives (2007)

Entrepreneurship

EABIS Research Project

Title: Corporate Responsibility & SMEs: EABIS European Knowledge Network

Executive Summary: The creation of this research network was intended to identify the knowledge gaps that exist in relation to SMEs and corporate responsibility, and to prioritise an academic research agenda to fill these key gaps. EABIS funding supported two meetings of academic and independent thought leaders, which in turn led to the publication of a successful special issue of the *Journal of Business Ethics*.

Budget: € 10.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: December 2005 to October 2006

Lead Partner(s): Durham Business School

Supporting Partner(s): Bocconi University, Brunel University, Copenhagen Business School, ESADE, Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School, European Commission DG Enterprise and Industry, The Copenhagen Centre

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): See below.

Editor Peer-Reviewed Special Issue Journal

Title: **Small and Medium-sized Enterprises & Corporate Social Responsibility: Identifying the Knowledge Gaps.**

Guest Editor(s): Moore, G. & Spence, L.

Journal Issue: Journal of Business Ethics, Volume 67, No. 3

Publisher: Springer

Date of Publication: September 2006

Table of Contents: Murillo, D. & Lozano, J.M. *SMEs and CSR: An approach to CSR in their own words*

Jenkins, H. *Small business champions for CSR*

Lepoutre, J. & Heene, A. *Investigating the impact of firm size on small business social responsibility: a critical review*

Roberts, S., Lawson, R. & Nicholls, J. *Generating regional-scale improvements in SME corporate responsibility performance: lessons from Responsibility Northwest*

Fuller, T. & Tian, Y. *Social and symbolic capital and responsible entrepreneurship: an empirical investigation of SME narratives*

Perrini, F. *SMEs and CSR theory: evidence and implications from an Italian perspective*

Williamson, D., Lynch-Wood, G. & Ramsay, J. *Drivers of Environmental Behaviour in Manufacturing SMEs and the implications for CSR*

Finance

EABIS Research Project

Title: **EU Alliance for CSR – Laboratory Initiative on Valuing Non-Financial Performance**

Executive Summary: This project is founded on a key contention – namely that ESG factors will be increasingly important determinants of non-financial performance as the influence of externalities such as climate change, public and regulatory expectations of

business, and the so-called 'war for talent' grow. The Laboratory developed a central framework of principles and recommendations for improved dialogue between companies and investors. These were then tested in extensive stakeholder dialogue and by a leading, independent academic research team (see below).

Budget: € 20.000

Funding Source: Lloyds TSB, Telecom Italia

Period: May 2007 to June 2009

Lead Partner(s): Lloyds TSB and Telecom Italia

Supporting Partner(s): EABIS, CSR EUROPE, Sodalitas, European Federation of Financial Analysts (EFFAS)

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): EU Alliance for CSR Lab Interim Report (Dec 2008): *Valuing Non-Financial Performance: A European Framework for Company and Investor Dialogue*.

Report due May 2010 (Leaders Forum).

EABIS Research Project

Title: Corporate Responsibility and Measuring the Financial and Non-Financial Performance of the Firm

Executive Summary: This project builds on a number of strands of academic and practitioner research. Earlier work for EABIS by Cranfield has looked at linking stakeholder and shareholder value and suggested a generic approach to identifying stakeholders' impact on corporate value. It also builds on previous literature reviews, meta-studies (on the link between environmental / social performance and economic performance), corporate practice, and the use of NFP metrics.

The aims of the project are to identify existing practices from both the business and investment communities with regard to non-financial metrics (or measurement), design effective non-financial metrics for both the business and investment communities, and analyse the potential/existing impediments (internal and external) in communicating non financial information to the financial community

Budget: € 100.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

- Period: June 2007 to September 2009
- Lead Partner(s): Doughty Centre, Cranfield University School of Management
- Participating schools: Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School, SDA Bocconi School of Management, University of Lille
- Internal Report(s): Academic literature review led by Bocconi on the link between corporate social and financial performance. "Going beyond a long-lasting debate: What is behind the relationship between corporate social and financial performance?" (2009)
- Academic literature review led by Vlerick on the practices of the SRI community and the potential for diffusion to non-SRI investors and analysts. 'Integration of extra-financial information into stock valuation: the role of collective beliefs' (2009)
- Academic literature review of C(S)R / sustainability reporting by Cranfield. This was published as a Working Paper: "*Non-Financial Performance Metrics for Corporate Responsibility Reporting Revisited*". (2009)
- Meta-analysis of more than 80 practitioner reports from think-tanks, business-led coalitions, international accounting and consultancy firms, company organisations and investor bodies on barriers to the communication and use of ESG/EFP data and prospects to overcome these obstacles. This is prepared by the Doughty Centre. (2009)
- External Publication(s): EU Alliance for CSR Lab Interim Report (2008): *Valuing Non-Financial Performance: A European Framework for Company and Investor Dialogue*.
- Final Research Report (2009): *Sustainable Value: Corporate Responsibility, Market Valuation and Measuring the Financial & Non-Financial Performance of the Firm*

Governance

EABIS Research Project

Title: The Changing Role of Government: The Relational State and its Implications for Corporate Responsibility

Executive Summary: This project set out with four main objectives:

- Analyse the changing role of government in promoting corporate responsibility to help policy-makers, business

leaders and academics to better understand the development of corporate responsibility public policies

- Develop an analytical framework to explore the potential of the role of government in shaping corporate responsibility-oriented governance
- Apply the Relational State Model and corporate responsibility-oriented governance as a methodology to explore the interactions between business, government and civil society organizations
- Apply the Relational State Model and collaborative history of exchange to three European countries: Italy, Norway and the United Kingdom.

Budget: € 21.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: March 2005 to March 2006

Lead Partner(s): ESADE Business School

Supporting Partner(s): Bocconi University / SDA Bocconi School of Management, Norwegian School of Management

Internal Report(s): Buckland, H., Albareda, L., Lozano, J.M., Tencati, A., Perrini, F. & Midttun, A. (2006). *The Changing Role of Government in Corporate Responsibility: A Report for Practitioners*.

External Publication(s): Albareda, L. (2005). *Literature review of the changing role of government: the relational state and its implications for corporate responsibility*. Institute of the Individual, Corporations and Society, ESADE.

Tencati, A. (2006). *Economic, Social, Environmental and Sustainability Performance Evaluation and Reporting at the National Level: Frameworks and Indicators*. "G. Pivato" Management Department, Bocconi University, and SDA Bocconi School of Management.

Albareda, L., Ysa, T. and Lozano, JM. (2005). *The role of governments in fostering CSR*. In Morsing, M. and Kakabadse, A. (Eds – 2005), *CSR – Reconciling Aspiration Through Application*, Palgrave, pp. 110-128.

Lozano, JM., Albareda, L. and Ysa, T. (2005). *¿Que pueden hacer los gobiernos para promover la Responsabilidad Social de la Empresa?. Responsabilidad Social de las Empresas y Economía Social, Revista de Economía Pública, Social y Cooperativa, Valencia, no 53*.

Midttun, A. (2005). *Realigning Business, Government and Civil Society: Emerging Relational Governance Beyond the (neo) Liberal and Welfare State Models*. Article for *Corporate*

Governance, The International Journal, Vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 159-174.

Morsing, M., Midttun, A., & Palmås, K. (2005). *Perspectives and Challenges on Corporate Social Responsibility in Scandinavia. The Debate over Corporate Social Responsibility*. May, S., Cheney, G., & Roper, J. (Eds). Oxford University Press.

Perrini, F. & Tencati A. (2005). *La Corporate Social Responsibility in Europa: sostenibilità dei modelli di sviluppo*, in S. Rosci (Ed.), *Il grande salto sociale. Percorsi di responsabilità delle imprese in Italia*. Naples: Controcorrente, 39-64.

EABIS Editor Peer-Reviewed Special Issue Journal

Title:	Corporate Responsibility and the Emerging Global Governance Paradigm
Guest Editor(s):	Lenssen, G., Arenas, D., Lacy, P. & Pickard, S.
Journal Issue:	<i>Corporate Governance, The International Journal of Business in Society</i> , Volume 8, number 4
Publisher:	Emerald Insight
Date of Publication:	September 2008
Table of Contents:	Exploring the Governance Agenda of Corporate Responsibility Keohane, R. <i>Complex Accountability and Power in Global Governance: Issues for Global Business</i> Maerki, H.U. <i>The Globally Integrated Enterprise and its Role in Global Governance</i> Zadek, S. <i>Global Collaborative Governance: "There Is No Alternative"</i> Mendoza, X. & Vernis, A. <i>The Changing Role of Governments and the Emergence of the Relational State</i> Delbard, O. <i>CSR Legislation in France and the European Regulatory Paradox: An Analysis of EU CSR Policy and Sustainability Reporting Practices</i> Global Governance and the Interface with Business: New Institutions, Processes and Partnerships

Midttun, A. *The Case for Partnered Governance: Aligning Corporate Responsibility and Public Policy in the Global Economy*

Kolk, A. & Pinkse, J. *Business and Climate Change: Emergent Institutions in Global Governance*

Albareda, L. *Corporate Responsibility, Governance and Accountability: From Self-Regulation to Co-Regulation*

Jackson, K. *Natural Law, Human Rights and Corporate Reputational Capital in Global Governance*

Arevalo, J. & Fallon, F. *Assessing Corporate Responsibility as a Contribution to Global Governance: the Case of the UN Global Compact*

Global Governance Challenges in Industry Sectors and Supply Chains

McPhail, K. *Contributing to Sustainable Development through Multi-Stakeholder Processes: Practical Steps to Avoid the 'Resource Curse'*

Sturchio, J. *Business Engagement in Public Programs: The Pharmaceutical Industry's Contribution to Public Health and the Millennium Development Goals*

Greve, J. *Healthcare in Developing Countries and the Role of Business: A Global Governance Framework to Enhance the Accountability of Pharmaceutical Companies*

Nijhof, A. *Managing Legitimacy Issues in Global Supply Chains: The Case of the Athletic Footwear Industry*

Tencati, A. *Unintended Consequences of CSR: Protectionism and Collateral Damage in Global Supply Chains*
Collaborative Governance: New Roles, Models and Strategies for the Firm

Paro, R. & Boechat, C. *Strategic Planning and the Millennium Development Goals in Brazilian Companies*

Raufflet, E., Berrager, A. & Gouin, J.-F. *Innovation in Business-Community Partnerships: Evaluating the Impact of Local Enterprise and Global Investment Models on Poverty, Bio-Diversity and Development*

Kourula, A. & Halme, M. *Types of Corporate Responsibility and Engagement with NGOs: An Exploration of Business and Societal Outcomes*

Healthcare

EABIS Research Stakeholder Dialogue

Title: Research Informed Practice in Healthcare: Leadership, Organisational Change, and Governance

Executive Summary: Providers and commissioners of healthcare are under pressure to meet escalating demands for high quality, cost effective services. The ability of nations to meet this challenge has significant implications for the wellbeing of its citizens and for economic performance.

Moreover, the private, public and voluntary healthcare sector is a major source of employment, and thus the way in which health organisations manage their human resources has significant impact on the quality of working life for large sections of the working population. National healthcare systems are under pressure to change, both nationally and internationally and are seeking innovative ways to expand services and improve quality within limited budgets.

There is a need to develop a stronger evidence base which can inform policy and practice in healthcare management, and to find effective ways of ensuring that research is relevant to practice. In particular there is a need for health organisations, businesses, service users, and other stakeholders to work together with academic researchers.

This EABIS project will fund a number of expert scholars, corporate managers and interested stakeholders to generate new ideas and explore different models of healthcare organisations internationally.

The group will pay particular attention to identifying lessons from Europe to complement the usual American base of research into healthcare organisational reform. Thus this international forum will explore what lessons can be learned by comparing and contrasting approaches to healthcare management and organisation across national boundaries and disseminate this learning through its education, training and professional development activities.

Budget: € 5.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: June 2009 – April 2010

Lead Partner(s): Kingston University Business School & School of Management, Royal Holloway University of London (Institute of Leadership and Management in Health).

Supporting Partner(s): N/A

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): N/A to date

Impact and Measurement

EU Research Project

Title: **IMPACT Project: Impact Measurement and Performance Analysis of CSR**

Executive Summary: The overall objective of the IMPACT Project is to assess, measure and monitor the economic, societal and environmental impacts arising from CSR policies and practices in Europe.

IMPACT intends to create and develop new and existing tools that measure the impacts of CSR at different levels across European companies, sectors, regions and EU27. It will seek to test and validate these tools through its research design. At the same time the research methods will provide evidence to explain, characterise and compare the relationship between the motivations and drivers of CSR in companies, their translation into actions, and their outcomes in terms of internal CSR performance and impacts for the company, economy, society and environment.

The research will focus on SMEs as well as large companies. Attention will be given to the structure and influence of regional, national and European institutions and settings on the CSR impacts of companies and their networks. The project will collate and combine existing non-public data sets that help to measure and monitor the impacts of CSR. It will initiate new panel data to monitor CSR impacts across Europe. The empirical evidence on the impacts of CSR will be used to establish a picture of the contribution by European companies through CSR to meeting the main areas and objectives set in the Lisbon and Gothenburg strategies - competitiveness (including innovation), growth, quality of jobs and sustainability.

Budget: € 2.600.000

Funding Source: EU 7th Research Framework Programme (FP7)

Period: March 2010 – June 2013

Lead Partner(s): EABIS and Öko Institut

Supporting Partner(s): Catholic University of Leuven, Central European University Business School, Centre for European Economic Research, Copenhagen Business School, Foundation CentERdata, Helsinki School of Economics, IESE, INSEAD, Institute for Social-Ecological Research, Leon Kozminski Academy of Entrepreneurship & Management, Nottingham University Business School, Politecnico di Milano, TiasNimbas Business School, Tilburg University, Vienna University of Economics & Business

Anticipated Outputs:

- A wide range of concept, synthesis and analytical papers on various aspects of impact performance measurement, policy frameworks, case studies and more
- Company case studies and in-depth interviews
- Delphi study
- Network analysis
- Econometric analysis
- Policy and strategy briefs
- Practical recommendations for corporates, SMEs and stakeholders to increase their CR impact on competitiveness, growth, quality of jobs and the environment
- Various working papers, communications and online resources generated by the multiple work packages built into the successful proposal

International Dimensions

EABIS Research Project

Title: Best Corporate Responsibility Performers in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE)

Executive Summary: This project makes a selection of the best social performers from CEE Top 500 based on a specially tailored assessment tool and aims to prepare a collection of educational case studies. Through analysis of the case studies, the research team will identify a set of best strategies that companies in CEE have used to implement Corporate Responsibility (CR) at the strategic level, at the same time including employees and other stakeholders in their business models.

In terms of relevance, CR has become a hot topic in CEE because of the region's increasing embeddedness into the global political and economic system in recent decade. There is an emerging need for integration of Corporate Responsibility

in the mainstream management education and executive education in CEE countries.

Budget: € 50.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: March 2010 – June 2011

Lead Partner(s): Leon Kozminski Academy of Entrepreneurship and Management (LKAEM)

Supporting Partner(s): Central European University Business School (CEU)

Anticipated Outputs:

- Easy to use and business relevant methodology for Performance Assessment of CR and Sustainability for companies operating in CEE.
- Collection of educational case studies from best CR performers in CEE for management educators.
- Working paper for practitioners on best strategies in CEE.
- TOP20: Good Company Ranking CEE – to be presented at 19th CEE Economic Forum Krynica, September 2009, the biggest event in CEE.
- Report for practitioners and corporate leaders in CEE with the working topic: Are there any specific patterns of business behaviour in CEE that can be discerned?

Leadership + Organisational Change

EABIS Research Project

Title: Management Competencies and Leadership Qualities for Corporate Responsibility

Executive Summary: This project was created to deliver a practical framework that could help companies and providers of management education to develop the socially responsible business leaders who could meet the business and management challenges of tomorrow.

The study looked at how organisations need to (collective and individual) develop knowledge sets, skills & abilities and personal qualities & mindsets within the context of organisational learning. It examined how these components in combination gave rise to key behaviours necessary to integrate responsible decision-making into day-to-day business practice.

Budget: € 52.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: February 2005 to June 2006

Lead Partner(s): Ashridge

Supporting Partner(s): N/A

Corporate Partner(s): BP, Cargill, Dexia Asset Management, ENI, IBM, Johnson & Johnson, Microsoft, Shell, Solvay, Suez & Unilever

Internal (s): Wilson, A., Lenssen, G., & Hinds, P. (2007). Practitioner Report: *Leadership Qualities and Management Competencies for Corporate Responsibility*.

External Publication(s): Wilson, A. (2006). *Taking on the complexity challenge. Ethical Corporation*.

Wilson, A. (2007). *Learning to lead responsibly. People Management*, Issue 1.

Wilson, A. (2007). *Developing Responsible Leaders. Leadership in Action*, special issue on leadership and sustainability. Jossey-Bass/Wiley.

EABIS Research Project

Title: Developing the Global Leaders of Tomorrow

Executive Summary: The Global Leaders of Tomorrow project was led by Ashridge in partnership with EABIS, the United Nations Global Compact Office, and an international consortium of EABIS member business schools. Its platform of activity was to design and implement a worldwide survey of corporate signatories to the UN Global Compact.

Its primary objective was to deliver the most comprehensive global mapping and quantified analysis of what business leaders worldwide will expect and require – in terms of skills, competences and awareness – from their next generations of managers. The insights derived from this process are intended to serve as a catalyst for change among business schools and management training providers, their services, programmes, and integration of business priorities into human capital development.

Budget: € 62.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: May 2008 to May 2009

Lead Partner(s): Ashridge Business School

Supporting Partner(s): Center for Creative Leadership, Graduate Schools of Business – University of Cape Town, EABIS, IEDC-Bled, IESE, INSEAD, University of Waikato, China Europe International Business School (CEIBS), EGADE – Universidad Tecnológico de Monterrey, Weatherhead School of Management – Case Western Reserve University, United Nations Global Compact Office.

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): Gitsham, M. (2008). *Developing the Global Leaders of Tomorrow* – Preliminary Report presented to UN Global Compact PRME Forum, UN HQ, New York.

Gitsham, M. & Lenssen, G. (2009). *Developing Global Leaders of Tomorrow*, Final Report.

EABIS Research Project

Title: LEAP – Leadership for Integrated Corporate Responsibility – Putting Vision into Practice

Executive Summary: This project's main focus is to develop an understanding of the leadership beliefs, practices and roles that translate Corporate Responsibility (CR) into integrated organisational and social practices and outcomes. The project has set up four main objectives:

- Corroborate and further develop the findings of earlier research on the roles, beliefs and practices that support leadership outcomes in terms of direction, alignment and commitment to CR as an integrated practice in companies
- Characterise these roles, beliefs and practices and specify their inter-relationships (develop a model); this can be used to design a leadership capability assessment tool or “Barometer”. The use of the barometer will inform an organisation about its leadership capacity. The barometer will be available for use in the EABIS network, with the provision of further guidance from the research team.
- Establish the hierarchy or sequence of practices that are expected to provide for effective leadership in CR
- Transfer knowledge from research findings to organisational practice through the development of master classes and leadership development programs for CR as an integrated practice

Budget: € 65,000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: March 2010 – July 2011

Lead Partner(s): Solvay Business School

Supporting Partner(s): Center for Creative Leadership

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): N/A to date

Editor Peer-Reviewed Special Issue Journal

Title: **Corporate Responsibility and Sustainability: Leadership & Organisational Change**

Guest Editor(s): Lensesen, G., Tyson, S., Bevan, D. & Pickard, S.

Journal Issue: *Corporate Governance, The International Journal of Business in Society*, Volume 9, number 4.

Publisher: Emerald Insight

Date of Publication: September 2009

Table of Contents: **Context: External Strategy and Internal Capability**

Zollo, M., Minoja, M., Casanova, L., Hockerts, K., Neergaard, P., Schneider, S. & Tencati, A. *Towards an Internal Change Management Perspective of CSR*

Castello, I. & Lozano, J.M. *CSR: Analysis of Strategic Drivers of Change*

White, P. *Building a Sustainability Strategy into the Business*

Overall Change Dynamics

Rake, M. & Grayson, D. *Embedding Corporate Responsibility*

Lopez, S. *Environmental Engagement, Organizational Capability and Firm Performance*

Bartlett, D. *Embedding Corporate Responsibility: A Transformational Model of Organisational Innovation*

Leadership of Organisational Change

D'Amato, A. & Roome, N. *Towards an Integrated Model of Leadership for Corporate Responsibility*

Bevan, D. & Gitsham, M. *Context, Complexity, Connectedness: Dimensions of Globalization Revealed*

Mostovicz, I., Kakabadse, N. & Kakabadse, A. *The Role of Leadership in Driving Ethical Outcomes*

People and Skills

Rok, B. *The Ethical Context of Participative Leadership: Taking People into Account*

Chun, R. *Corporate Responsibility to Employees During a Merger: Organisational Virtue and Employee Loyalty*

Lacy, P., Arnott, J. & Lowitt, E. *The Challenge of Integrating Sustainability into Talent and Organisation Strategies: Investing in the Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes to Achieve High Performance*

Organisational Structures and Processes

Spitzek, H. *The Development of Governance Structures for Corporate Responsibility*

Perera Adalma, L.R., Awad Amar, P. & Winicki Trostianki, D. *Embedding Through Effective Organisational Structures*

Preuss, L. & Cordoba-Pachon, J.-R. *A Knowledge Management Perspective of CSR*

Jacopin, T. & Fontrodona, J. *Questioning the CR Department Alignment with the Business Model of the Company*

Projects in Planning

EABIS Research Project

Title: **Building Capacity for Sustainability through a UN Global Compact Learning Network**

Executive Summary: Despite the success of its first 10 years, the UN Global Compact remains for many of its signatory organizations a statement of intent, a commitment to achieve highly ambitious goals that is followed up to highly varying degrees by concrete internal change processes at the strategic, operating, and/or cultural levels.

It would be important, in fact, to build on the significant efforts produced over the years to develop insights from clinical case studies of GC companies, and to establish the structures and processes necessary to develop a collective learning process capable to address the “learning gap” between the commitments made and the actual capacity to enact the

fundamental organizational changes required to turn the aspirations into sustainable strategies, practices and mindsets.

Under this project proposal, this challenge would be addressed by developing an “engaged learning platform” formed by a global network of research centers that will commit to a long-term research and action-learning intervention program to help GC companies develop the required capabilities to embed the 10 Principles into their strategic and operating processes.

The core strategy to tackle the “learning gap” is based on leveraging existing relationships among research centers and leading scholars to create the first global network of corporate responsibility/sustainability development (CR/SD) experts committed to the systematic collection and analysis of data related to internal change initiatives implemented by GC signatories, and their results in terms of social, environmental and economic impacts.

Budget: € 3.000.000 (* estimated)

Funding Source(s): EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme (minimum pilot phase)
UN Global Compact Signatory Companies (main implementation phase)

Period: March 2011 – July 2011 (pilot phase)
July 2011 – December 2020 (main implementation phase)

Lead Partner(s): SDA Bocconi School of Management, Università Bocconi

Supporting Partner(s): EABIS, INSEAD, EABIS Corporate Founding Partners, UN Global Compact

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): N/A to date

EABIS Research Project

Title: Corporate Responsibility and the Social Value of Brands

Executive Summary: Trust in business has plummeted. The 10th annual edition of the Edelman Trust Barometer [2009] reveals that overall, 62% of respondents trust business less than they did a year ago. Different markets show widely dispersed results: in the US, trust in business has shown unprecedented decreases to levels below the time of the ENRON scandal; whereas in the Netherlands respondents who believe that business will “do what is right” has increased from 55% to 62% compared to a year ago.

Social model economies, such as the Netherlands and Sweden (35% → 51%), are in fact the only geographies where trust in business has increased. However, they show very different trust levels in respect to trust in government (in the Netherlands general trust has increased from 64% to 74%, whereas the same figures in Sweden has declined from 63% to 39%).

The social contract between business, government and key stakeholders (including consumers) is rapidly being redefined. And stakeholders are looking at business and government to strike up collaborative frameworks to address the critical issues facing society today; in response to whether Business has lost ability to lead unilaterally and should partner with others to solve global issues; 65% in the EU responded positively, whereas 30% felt that business should “go at it” unilaterally, and 4% didn’t see a role for business.

This sets a context where companies’ role in shaping – collaboratively with stakeholders and governments – consumer / stakeholder behaviours that will have critical impact on local, regional, national and global issues is significantly increasing in importance.

EABIS is planning a joint research initiative with Corporate Founding Partner **Unilever** and a select team of academic experts to assess: how can companies most effectively influence positive consumer behaviour, and what are key areas where such behavioural change can be impacted? How can the strength of a disperse set of product brands be leveraged into the corporate brand (and vice versa)?

Secondly, and more importantly, the project intends to examine how existing brands can be used to leverage a stronger “social accountability” message that go beyond merely reacting to stakeholder (-consumer) expectations, but rather driving actual consumer behaviours. What might be the new models for business to actively influence sustainable / positive social behaviours among end-users in the value chain (detergent use; water use; etc)? And by extension is it possible to identify means whereby this positive 3rd party behaviour can be associated with the corporate brand?

This research project will also tie into parallel INSEAD- and Durham-led EABIS research around consumer perceptions and the “halo effect” that separate brand activities are likely to have on overall corporate brands.

Budget: € 70.000 – 140.000 (* tbd)

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: November 2009 – March 2011

Lead Partner(s): Manchester Business School

Supporting Partner(s): Bath Business School, Henley Management College (Reading University), Copenhagen Business School, INSEAD, Mannheim University, Bentley University, EABIS Corporate Network

Corporate Partner(s): Unilever

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): N/A to date

EABIS Research Project

Title: Corporate Responsibility and Healthcare: Access, Infrastructure and Resources

Executive Summary: EABIS is planning a joint research initiative with Corporate Founding Partner **Johnson & Johnson** and a select team of academic experts to assess: new forms of organisation, the impact of irregular governance outside of the “traditional” OECD country paradigm, and brand and organisational development around e-health.

The research will take a particular focus on the European, Middle Eastern and African (EMEA) region, reflecting the scope of corporate responsibility & citizenship activity for many of EABIS’ corporate members – who will also be invited to shape research design, priority issues, objectives and deliverables.

Budget: € 70.000 – 140.000 (* tbd)

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: November 2009 – July 2011

Lead Partner(s): Johnson & Johnson

Supporting Partner(s): Rutgers University, INSEAD, Royal Holloway University of London, Kingston University, EABIS Corporate Network

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): N/A to date

Title: From IT to ET: Enabling Technologies, European Growth and the Changing Role of Business in 21st Century Society

Executive Summary: EABIS is supporting a pioneering transatlantic research initiative with Corporate Founding Partner **Microsoft** and a select team of academic experts to assess: new forms of organisation, the impact of irregular governance outside of the “traditional” OECD country paradigm, and brand and organisational development around e-health.

This research project seeks to deliver empirical/academic analysis of the size and potential of the market for so-called Enabling Technologies (ICT embedded Intelligence and habit-changing ICT) in Europe, with reference to the evolution of global markets. The project will also deliver recommendations on how ET can contribute to addressing the European Union’s major environmental, social and economic challenges, over the five-year mandate of the next European Commission, from 2009 until 2014, in 4 specific areas: healthcare/aging population; climate change/low carbon economy; education; and governance.

The project has three target audiences:

Academic: the project will generate new knowledge about the evolution of ET in Europe and its implications for overall European competitiveness as well as the specific evolution of critical sectors of the European economy;

Business: the study will identify major business opportunities in the coming five to ten years on ET- related issues;

Policy: the study will identify key trends in the four core areas outlined above and how enabling technologies may help policy leaders in EU Member States, the European Parliament and European Commission address attendant societal challenges and economic opportunities.

Research work is being organized into four different sectoral “clusters” in the areas of healthcare/aging population; climate change/low carbon economy; education; and governance. A research team is being organized for each sectoral cluster. Each cluster is headed by a cluster team leader, drawing on the efforts of mutually-agreed research team members and cooperating partners.

The overall project is being coordinated by Johns Hopkins University, but will be supported by various EABIS academic institutions to integrate the European perspective into the core of the initiative.

Budget: € 400.000 (* US\$ 650.000)

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: September 2009 – December 2010

Lead Partner(s): Microsoft, Johns Hopkins University

Supporting Partner(s): Warwick Business School, Imperial College London, EABIS Academic Network, Johnson & Johnson

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): N/A to date

EABIS Research Project

Title: **Practical Wisdom for Management from the Spiritual and Philosophical Traditions**

Executive Summary: The financial crisis and the fear of more systemic upheaval in the global economy have ignited a debate on the value of practical wisdom in management and management education.

The root causes of the recent financial crisis have been debated extensively. Despite the assumption that abundant information had been mathematically modelled and that knowledge of the working of markets had been researched, spectacular miscalculations and failures occurred. Remedies for better regulation and more effective incentives have been devised, but has real learning taken place? And, beyond systemic failures, what about personal responsibilities?

EABIS and Yale University have recently formed a unique partnership to advance global dialogue and understanding in this domain, through an international series of conferences on practical wisdom for management from the world's spiritual and philosophical traditions (including the Christian, Islamic, Hindu-Vedic, Jain, Jewish, Buddhist, Chinese classical and Humanist traditions), addressing the central question: *How can we bring back the value of wisdom in management and management education?* See below for a provisional timetable of the conferences.

The focus of these seminars and publications is to provide an interdisciplinary engagement among theology, philosophy, business and economics on the virtue of practical wisdom and business practice so as to both deepen our understanding of practical wisdom and its relationship to business and management.

Thematic Focus	Time Line	Host Institution	Location
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Chinese Classical Traditions	18-19 June, 2010	ECCLAR Centre, CEIBS International Business School	Shanghai, China
Hindu-Vedic Tradition	Autumn 2010	Conscious Capitalism Centre, Bentley University	Waltham, MA. USA
Islamic Tradition	Autumn 2010	Tabah Foundation for Islamic Studies	Abu Dhabi, UAE
Jewish Tradition	Spring 2011	Mandel Leadership Institute	Jerusalem, Israel
Buddhist Tradition	Autumn 2011	Thammasat University Business School	Bangkok, Thailand
Jain Tradition	Spring 2012	TBC	India
Humanist Tradition	Autumn 2012	TBC	Europe
Closing Global Conference	Spring 2013	Yale University	New Haven, CT, USA

Budget: TBD

Funding Source: EABIS, Yale University, and sponsorship from various international corporations and foundations

Period: Autumn 2009 – Autumn 2013

Lead Partner(s): EABIS, Yale University

Supporting Partner(s): Catholic University of Eichstätt, University of St. Thomas Minnesota, CEIBS International Business School, EFMD, Bentley University, Tabah Foundation for Islamic Studies Abu Dhabi, Mandel Leadership Institute (to date)

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): A Special Issue of the *Journal of Management Development* will be published following each international seminar on individual traditions.

See below for details of the first Special Issue publication.

Editor Peer-Reviewed Special Issue Journal

Title: **Practical Wisdom for Management from the Christian Tradition**

Guest Editor(s): Naughton, M., Habisch, A. & Lenssen, G.

Journal Issue: *Journal of Management Development*, Volume and number TBD.

Publisher: Emerald Insight

Date of Publication: August 2010

Table of Contents: **Academic Papers:**

Loza Adai, C. & Habisch, A. *Seasoning Business Knowledge: Challenging Recent Catholic Social Thought.*

Alford, H. *The Practical Wisdom of Personalism.*

Clark, C. *Practical Wisdom and Understanding the Economy.*

Cornuel, E., Habisch, A., & Kletz, P. *Practical Wisdom and the Catholic Social Tradition.*

Grassl, W. *Aquinas on Management and its Development.*

Hoebeke, L. *The Decalogue and Practical Wisdom: Re-reading a Seminal Text.*

Lenssen, G. *Practical Wisdom: The Value of Text Exegesis.*

Maines, D. & Naughton, M. *Middle Level Thinking: The Cultural Mission of Business Schools.*

Melé, D. *Practical Wisdom in Managerial Decision-Making.*

Meynhardt, T. *The Practical Wisdom of Peter Drucker: Roots in the Christian Tradition.*

Molteni, M. & Pedrini, M. *In Search of Socio-Economic Syntheses.*

Tredget, D. *Practical Wisdom and the Rule of Benedict.*

Weber-Berg, C. *Practical Wisdom: An Attempt for a Protestant Re-formulation.*

Practitioner Papers:

Brinkmann, W.R. & O'Brien, D. *Transforming Healthcare: A Study in Practical Wisdom.*

Malloch, T.R. *Spiritual Capital.*

Mortreuil, L. *The Current Crisis: Who is to Blame?*

Research Mapping

EU Research Project

Title: **The European Platform for Excellence in CSR Research (a.k.a. CSR PLATFORM)**

Executive summary: The purpose of the CSR Platform Project was to mobilise researchers in supporting and developing excellence in research on corporate responsibility and business in society issues in the European Research Area (ERA).

The Project framework was developed around a number of central perceptions about the “state of the art” in CSR research in the early years of this decade. It set out to address a number of identified barriers and failures that were hindering real progress in terms of CSR research content, structure, approaches and coordination. Throughout its implementation phase, the Platform had as its foundation three strategic priorities:

- To mobilise an international community of researchers across disciplines, within disciplines, and across types of research
- To foster cooperation, participation and co-ownership in bringing CSR research forward between academia, the business community, policy makers and other key stakeholders
- To put in place an effective dissemination and integration system which would exploit past, current, and future European research projects, initiatives and outcomes on CSR-related issues for the benefit of all stakeholders

Budget: € 750.000

Funding Source: EU 6th Research Framework Programme (FP6)

Period: September 2004 to September 2008

Lead Partner(s): EABIS

Supporting Partner(s): Ashridge, Copenhagen Business School, The Copenhagen Centre, Cranfield School of Management, CSR Europe, EFMD, INSEAD, Katholische Universität Eichstätt – Ingolstadt, Leon Kozminski Academy of Management, Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School, Warsaw School of Economics, Warwick Business School

Internal Report(s): Crouch, C. (2006). *Modelling the firm in its market and organisational environment: methodologies for studying corporate social responsibility*.

Plackett, P. (2006). *Corporate responsibility and the role of business in society in Europe: Findings of the EABIS Business Members Knowledge and Learning Priorities workshop*.

Gitsham, M. & Noterdaeme, J. (2007). *Stakeholder Engagement in CSR Research through Multi-Stakeholder Processes: A preliminary study of the state of the art in Europe*.

External Publication(s): Roome, N. & Pickard, S. (2008). *CSR Platform Green Book Report: Building Europe's Reference Point for CSR Research – A Consortium Report to the European Commission (DG RTD)*.

EABIS Conferences: Multi-Stakeholder Research Colloquia

Overview: From 2002 EABIS has organised an Annual Multi-Stakeholder Colloquium, bringing together an international research community and stakeholders to build partnerships, identify key knowledge gaps and discuss potential new approaches to business in society research. Each year the event brings together 350 senior figures from business, academia, policy and independent research institutes.

From 2004 until 2007, the Colloquia were an integral part of the framework of the CSR Platform Project, making a vital contribution to the consolidation of a fragmented European research community. Their central themes have mostly addressed external dimensions of corporate responsibility:

2002 “Corporate Responsibility and Mapping Business Relevant Research Questions”
INSEAD

2003 “Managing Corporate Responsibility: the Moral Case or the Business Case”
Copenhagen Business School

2004 “Corporate Responsibility and Responding to Societal Expectations”
Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School

2005 “Corporate Responsibility and Competitiveness”
Leon Kozminski Academy of Entrepreneurship & Management

- 2006 “Corporate Responsibility and Strategic Management”**
SDA Bocconi School of Management
- 2007 “Corporate Responsibility and the Emerging Global Governance Paradigm”**
ESADE Business School
- 2008 “Corporate Responsibility, Leadership and Organisational Change”**
Cranfield University School of Management
- 2009 “The Role of Business in Society and Challenges for Corporate and Global Governance”**
IESE Business School
- 2010 “Corporate Responsibility and Emerging Economies” *****
St Petersburg State University School of Management
- 2011 “Corporate Responsibility and Development” *****
INSEAD

(*** = anticipated)

The Colloquia provided a central, unifying forum for the CSR Platform – a coherent space in the annual calendar, where academic researchers and research stakeholder could come together to share findings and ideas in a face-to-face setting, and link progress within their own research and work programmes.

Outcomes:

Reports on each Colloquium captured the process and outcomes of the event. In addition to presenting, sharing and disseminating knowledge on CR, the colloquia provided the ground for researchers to identify new research partners and to develop new research projects.

The Colloquia generated **almost 450 submissions of CR research-based inputs** during the same period. Practitioners were also encouraged to write and deliver research papers, alone or in collaboration with academic researchers. Collectively **over 600 research papers, presentations and debates** took place during the four colloquia with the best papers published and disseminated through the Knowledge Centre and journals. In addition to providing a way to meet and present research and share ideas, researchers and others began to form research clusters to develop research along common lines, while some have begun to explore new research issues and themes.

Website:

<http://www.eabis.org/colloquium/eabis-annual-colloquium-4.html>

Social & Environmental Issues

EABIS Research Project

Title: **Social and Environmental Aspects in Business and Management (SEABUS)**

Executive Summary: The project is called "International Research Network on Social and Environmental Aspects in Business and Management" and will run for three years. It is funded by the German Federal Ministry for Research and Education.

The main purpose of the project is to establish a network of researchers of the field that serves as a platform for exchange, discussion and further development of different research activities and ideas among the partners.

The overall target of the funding programme as well as of the project is to integrate the research of the network partners stronger into the academic mainstream.

In other words, the network is meant to help the network partners to better integrate their research in the area of environmental and social aspects of business and management with the mainstream academic position and by doing so strengthening both the academic record as well as the visibility of the network partner's research activities.

Budget: € 430.000 (approx.)

Funding Source: German Federal Ministry of Education and Research

Period: February 2007 – October 2009

Lead Partner(s): Institute for Futures Studies and Technology Assessment (IZT)

Supporting Partner(s): EABIS, Royal Holloway College (University of London) School of Management, University of Amsterdam Business School, Center for Business and the Environment at Yale University, University of St. Andrews, University of Hong Kong, University of Victoria (Canada), Queen's University Management School, Umeå School of Business

Internal Report(s): EABIS (2009). How do CSR and Sustainability Research Generate useful Inputs for Companies? Executive Summary of the SEABUS Workshop Report.

External Publication(s): Hahn, T., Kolk, A. & Winn, M. (forthcoming 2009). *Creating a New Future for Business: Rethinking Management Theory and Business Strategy in the Light of Rapid and Drastic Environmental and Social Changes*. A Special Issue of Business & Society.

Eds. TBD (forthcoming 2010). *Trade-Offs in Corporate Responsibility*. A Special Issue of Business Strategy & Environment.

Stakeholders

EABIS Research Project

Title: **Good Practices in Stakeholder Management**

Executive Summary: Based on a previous initiative carried out by the research team ('Redefining the Corporation – Stakeholder Management and Organizational Wealth'), this project expanded upon the empirical basis of those cases (Shell, Motorola, and more) by concentrating on multinational corporations based in Switzerland. The research evaluated good stakeholder management practices and tools based on analyses at the company, intra-industry and inter-industry levels, while in parallel examining:

- The firm's reason to pursue a broader stakeholder orientation and how this stakeholder orientation supports the firm's value creation process
- How this stakeholder orientation is reflected in the firm's strategy, structure and culture
- The identification of driving and hindering factors that emerge when implementing a stakeholder orientation, and whether specific reporting exists for this.

Budget: € 70.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: March 2005 to June 2007

Lead Partner(s): University of Applied Sciences in Business Administration, Zurich (HWZ)

Supporting Partner(s): EABIS, Forum Stakeholder View, Swiss Department for Foreign Affairs, Swiss Federal Office for Professional Education and Training, Ecoscientia Foundation

Internal Report(s): N/A

External Publication(s): See below

Research Articles & Presentations:

Kern, I., Sachs, S., & Rühli, E. (2006). "How Stakeholder Relations Pay Off by Maintaining the License to Operate: A

Comparative Case Study of the Swiss Telecommunications Industry." *Corporate Governance, The International Journal of Business in Society*, Volume 5, number 4.

Sachs, S., & Maurer, M. (Forthcoming). "Toward Dynamic Corporate Stakeholder Responsibility." *Journal of Business Ethics*.

Sachs, S., & Käslin, D. (2007). "Methodology at the Crossroads: Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis of Comparative Case Studies." Conference Proceedings of the International Association for Business and Society (IABS), Annual Meeting in Florence, Italy.

Sachs, S., Rühli, E., & Kern, I. (2007). "Stakeholder Relations as a Corporate Core to Operate, Compete and Innovate." Conference Proceedings of the International Association for Business and Society (IABS), Annual Meeting in Florence, Italy.

Sachs, S., Rühli, E., & Mittnacht, V. (2007). "How stakeholder relations impact corporate strategy – An empirical investigation." Conference Proceedings of the International Association for Business and Society (IABS), Annual Meeting in Florence, Italy.

Käslin D. (2007). "Structure and Agency in Firm-Stakeholder Networks." Conference Proceedings of the International Association for Business and Society (IABS), Annual Meeting in Florence, Italy.

Perrin I. (2007). "The role of the mass media as stakeholders in conferring corporate legitimacy." Conference Proceedings of the International Association for Business and Society (IABS), Annual Meeting in Florence, Italy.

Sachs, S., & Groth, H. (2007). „Aufwachen, bevor es zu spät ist: Die Schweizer Pharmaindustrie und ihre Stakeholder-Beziehungen.“ *IO New Management*, 4

Sachs, S., Maurer, M., Rühli, E., & Hoffmann, R. (2006). "Corporate Social Responsibility from a Stakeholder View Perspective: CSR Implementation by a Swiss Mobile Telecommunications Provider." *Corporate Governance* Vol. 6, no. 4: pp 506-515.

Books & Chapters:

Sachs, S., Rühli, E., & Kern, I. (2007). *Lizenz zum Managen. Mit Stakeholdern zum Erfolg: Herausforderungen und Good Practices*. Bern: Haupt Verlag.

(See below for details of English translation.)

Sachs, S., & Rühli, E. (2005). "Practical Issues in Implementing the Stakeholder View as a Core Competence." In Sanchez, R. & Heene, A. (Eds.), *Competence Perspectives on Resources, Stakeholders and Renewal*, Advances in Applied Business Strategy Volume 9, Oxford: Elsevier: 217-233.

EABIS Branded Book

Title: **Sustainable Success with Stakeholders - The Untapped Potential**

Author(s) / Editor(s): Sybille Sachs, Edwin Rühli & Isabelle Kern, HWZ Zurich

Publisher: Palgrave MacMillan

Date of Publication: October 2009

Summary: This book shows managers how they can identify their stakeholders and cooperate with them in a mutually successful and satisfying way. It includes numerous examples from the case studies and from international firms, illustrating the stepping stones to a comprehensive stakeholder management.

EABIS Branded Book

Title: **Inside the Mind of the Stakeholder: The Hype Behind Stakeholder Pressure**

Author(s) / Editor(s): Ulrich Steger, IMD

Publisher: Palgrave Macmillan

Date of Publication: September 2006

Summary: It is a well-known claim today that pressure on companies to become more responsible is increasing. However, is this based on fact or is merely wishful-thinking? The evidence obtained across nine stakeholder groups in Europe is sobering indeed in the context of globalization and the constant striving for competitiveness. This book provides an honest and in-depth analysis of how stakeholders themselves assess and influence corporate sustainability. It is an eye-opener, both for companies and for the stakeholders.

Editor Peer-Reviewed Special Issue Journal

Title: **Corporate Responsibility and Responding to Societal Expectations: The Challenge of Sustainable Growth.**

Guest Editor(s): Lenssen, G., Van Den Berghe, L. & Louche, C.

Journal Issue: *Corporate Governance, The International Journal of Business in Society*, Volume 5, number 3

Publisher: Emerald Insight

Date of Publication: September 2005

Table of Contents: **Governance**

Cornelius, P. *Good corporate practices in poor corporate governance systems: some evidence from the Global Competitiveness Report*

Ricart, J.E., Rodríguez, M.A. & Sanchez, P. *Sustainability in the boardroom: an empirical examination of Dow Jones Sustainability World Index leaders*

Strategy

Cumming, J.F., Bettridge, N. & Toyne, P. *Responding to global business critical issues: a source of innovation and transformation for FTSE 350 companies?*

Sachs, S., Rühli, E. & Mittnacht, V. *A CSR framework due to multiculturalism: the Swiss Re case*

Marketing and Market Development

Denby Wilkes, V. *Dealing with a global issue: contributing to poverty alleviation*

Aqueveque, C. *Signalling corporate values: consumers' suspicious minds*

Leadership, Learning and Human Resource Management

Martin, A. & Ernst, C. *Exploring leadership in times of paradox and complexity*

Roper, J. & Cheney, G. *The meanings of social entrepreneurship today*

Operations and Supply Chain Management

Fossgard-Moser, T. *Social performance: key lessons from recent experiences within Shell*

Blowfield, M. *Going global: how to identify and manage societal expectations in supply chains (and the consequences of failure)*

Finance and Accounting

Van de Velde, E., Vermeir, W. & Corten, F. *Corporate social responsibility and financial performance*

Guyatt, D. *Meeting objectives and resisting conventions: a focus on institutional investors and long-term responsible investing*

Policy Making and the Role of Government

Körner, K. *Changing governance patterns and CSR*

Midttun, A. *Realigning business, government and civil society: emerging embedded relational governance beyond the (neo) liberal and welfare state models*

Strategic Management

EU funded Research Project

Title: **RESPONSE Project - Understanding and Responding to Societal Demands on Corporate Responsibility**

Executive Summary: An INSEAD-led team of 5 partners and 20 Multi-National Corporations conducted a comprehensive study of societal and stakeholder demands on business decisions and actions from a business strategy and organisational change perspective

Project findings were based on comprehensive research data from:

- Survey of 1000 executives
- Deep structured interviews with 210 senior managers
- 217 interviews with representatives from 180 stakeholder organisations
- 19 sector-based case studies

Budget: € 1.100.000

Funding Source: EU 6th Research Framework Programme (FP6)

Period: July 2004 to October 2007

Lead Partner(s): INSEAD

Supporting Partner(s): Copenhagen Business School, SDA Bocconi School of Management
Leon Kozminski Academy of Management, Impact

Internal Report(s): Forstater, M., Zollo, M., Lacy, P. (2007). *Understanding Corporate Responsibility: An Executive Briefing – Findings and Insights from Project RESPONSE.* EABIS-INSEAD Special Publication.

External Publication(s): Lewicka-Strzalecka, A. (2006). *Opportunities and limitations of CSR in the postcommunist countries: the Polish case.* Corporate Governance vol. 6 no. 4, 440-448.

Lewicka-Strzalecka, A. (2006). *Spoleczna odpowiedzialnosc biznesu w Polsce: ograniczenia i perspektywy.* Annales 9, Etyka w zyciu gospodarczym, Salezjanska Wyzsza Szkola Ekonomii i Zarzadzania, Lodz, 285-294. (In Polish).

Lewicka-Strzalecka, A. (2007). *In Search of Corporate Social Responsibility Essence.* Praxiology: The International Annual of Practical Philosophy and Methodology Vol. 15, p.289-298.

Ringov, D. & Zollo, M. (2007). *The Impact of National Culture on Corporate Social Responsibility.* Corporate Governance vol. 7 no. 4, 476-485.

Zollo M., Crilly, D., Casanova, L., Hockerts, K., Minoja, M., Neergaard, P., Pedersen, E., Schneider, S., Tencati, A., Sloan, P. (2007). *Understanding and Responding to Societal Demands on Corporate Responsibility: A Consortium Report to the European Commission (DG RTD).*

Crilly, D., Schneider, S.C., & Zollo, M. (2008). *Psychological Antecedents to Socially Responsible Behavior.* European Management Review, 5(3): 175-190.

Lewicka-Strzalecka, A. (2008). *Spoleczna odpowiedzialnosc wielkich korporacji w swietle badan projektu RESPONSE.* Master of Business Administration 3(92), 29-33. (In Polish)

Pedersen, E.R. (2009). *Modelling CSR: How Managers Understand the Responsibilities of Business towards Society.* Forthcoming in Journal of Business Ethics.

Pedersen, E.R & Neergaard, P. (2009). *What Matters to Managers? The Whats, Whys, and Hows of Corporate Social Responsibility in a Multinational Corporation.* Forthcoming in Management Decision.

Sloan, Pamela. *Redefining Stakeholder Engagement: From Control to Collaboration,* Journal of Corporate Citizenship, Vol. 36 (forthcoming) (originally published in French in Gestion, Vol. 34: 79-89, 2009)

Sloan, Pamela. *L'engagement des dirigeants envers les parties prenantes: condition de succès de la responsabilité sociale et du développement durable*, Gestion - revue internationale de gestion Vol. 34: 79-89, (2009)

Zollo, M., Minoja, M., Casanova, L., Hockerts, K., Neergaard, P., Schneider, S., Tencati, A. (2009). *Context: external strategy and internal capability. Towards an internal change management perspective of CSR: evidence from project RESPONSE on the sources of cognitive alignment between managers and their stakeholders, and their implications for social performance*. Corporate Governance, Volume 9 Issue 4: 355-372 (2009).

Working Papers: Hockerts, K., Casanova, L., Gradillas, M., Sloan, P. & Jensen, E. (2008). *An Overview of CSR Practices: Project RESPONSE Benchmarking Report*. Browsing Working Paper, Kobenhavn 2008.

Crilly, D., Sloan, P. *The cognitive scope of the firm: Psychological antecedents to stakeholder salience*.

Crilly, D., Zollo, M., & Hansen, M. *The eye of the beholder: When symbolic compliance fails in the context of corporate social responsibility*.

Crilly, D., Zollo, M., & Hansen, M. *The contested corporation: Ideological conflict and decoupling in corporate social responsibility*.

EABIS Branded Book

Title: **Business Logic for Sustainability - A Food and Beverage Industry Perspective**

Author: Aileen Ionescu-Somers and Ulrich Steger, IMD

Publisher: Palgrave Macmillan

Date of publication: July 2008

Summary: The food and beverage sector, with some of the world's most well known and consumed brands, is vulnerable to pressure from worried consumers, concerned NGOs and other stakeholders to re-evaluate its environmental and social impacts. This book presents the results of a research project focused on the management challenges that sustainable development presents to food and beverage companies. From both quantitative and qualitative empirical evidence collected from managers over several years, we present an analysis that can help business managers from all industries in formulating a more robust business case for sustainability in their

organizations. This book is a veritable reality check against increasing levels of hype surrounding the subject of sustainable development over the last few years.

Editor Peer-Reviewed Special Issue Journal

Title:	Corporate Responsibility and Strategic Management.
Guest Editor(s):	Lenssen, G., Perrini, F., Tencati, A. & Lacy, P.
Journal Issue:	<i>Corporate Governance, The International Journal of Business in Society</i> , Volume 7, number 4
Publisher:	Emerald Insight
Date of Publication:	September 2007
Table of Contents:	Strategic Management, Corporate Responsibility and Stakeholder Management
	<i>Katsoulakos, T. & Katsoulacos, Y. Integrating corporate responsibility principles and stakeholder approaches into mainstream strategy: a stakeholder-oriented & integrative strategic management framework</i>
	<i>Kolk, A. & Pinkse, J. Towards strategic stakeholder management? Integrating perspectives on sustainability challenges such as corporate responses to climate change</i>
	<i>Foo, L.M. Stakeholder engagement in emerging economies: considering the strategic benefits of stakeholder management in a cross cultural and geopolitical context</i>
	<i>Moir, L., Kennerley, M. & Ferguson, D. Measuring the business case: linking stakeholder and shareholder value</i>
	Corporate Responsibility from a Resource & Knowledge Perspective
	<i>Midttun, A. Towards a dynamic reinterpretation of C(S)R: are corporate responsibility and innovation compatible or contradictory?</i>
	<i>Holmes, S. & Moir, L. Developing a conceptual framework to identify corporate innovations through engagement with non-profit stakeholders</i>
	<i>Knecht, F. & Calenbuhr, V. Using capital transaction due diligence to demonstrate CSR assessment in practice</i>

Vélaz, I., Sison, A.J.G. & Fontrodona, J. *Incorporating CSR and stakeholder management into corporate strategy: a case study of the CAN experience 2002-2006*

Corporate Responsibility from an Industry Structure Perspective

Kern, I., Sachs, S. & Rühli, E. *Stakeholder relations and maintaining the license to operate: a comparative case study of the Swiss telecommunications Industry*

Davies, I.A. *The eras and participants of Fair Trade: an industry structure / stakeholder perspective on the growth of the fair trade industry*

Zappi, G. *Corporate responsibility in the Italian banking industry: creating value through listening to stakeholders*

Corporate Responsibility from a Social-Institutional Perspective

Ringov, D. & Zollo, M. *The impact of national culture on corporate social performance*

Bzdak, M. *The Johnson & Johnson Bridge to Employment Initiative: building sustainable community education partnerships*

Mair, J. & Marti, I. *Entrepreneurship for social impact: encouraging market access in rural Bangladesh*

Corporate Responsibility in Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprises

Kusyk, S.M. & Lozano, J.M. *SME social performance: a four cell typology of key drivers and barriers on social issues and their implications for stakeholder theory*

Sweeney, L. *Corporate Social Responsibility in Ireland: barriers and opportunities experienced by SMEs when undertaking CSR*

Fernández Fernández, J.L., Benavides Delgado, J. & Villagra García, N. *Bodega Jiménez-Landi and Javier Benjumea Chair: the collaborative creation of a strategic stakeholder management approach in a small Spanish enterprise*

Closing Reflection

Donaldson, T. *“Ethical Blowback”: The missing piece in the corporate governance puzzle – the risks to a company which fails to understand and respect its social contract.*

Supply Chain

EABIS Research Project

Title: **Implementing Environmental and Social Supply Chain Policy: Learning from Corporate Experience**

Executive Summary: This co-operative and interdisciplinary project between three research-based institutions in the UK, Italy and Germany is concerned with the effective implementation of environmental and social supply chain policy within companies. Although a great deal is known about the incidence and determinants of corporate environmental and social supply chain policy, and the implementation of such policies in supply relationships, little is known about the way in which policy is transformed into action, or the barriers which restrict action within companies.

Earlier work suggests that a significant gap exists between policy statements and practical implementation in companies which reflects incentive structures in supply management and top management support for implementation. This project will explore the relationship between corporate environmental and social strategy and supply chain environmental and social strategy before evaluating the role and efficiency of the underlying tools which are central to the development and implementation of effective environmental and social supply chain policy within the company.

Budget: € 60.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: September 2009 – December 2010

Lead Partner(s): CBOS University of Bath

Supporting Partner(s): ALTIS Catholic University of Milan, Catholic University of Eichstätt-Ingolstadt

Internal Report(s): N/A to date

External Publication(s): N/A to date

Surveys

EABIS Research Project

Title: **EABIS-Nottingham Survey of Teaching and Research in Europe on CSR**

Executive Summary: In light of some criticism about social responsibility education in business schools, this survey – addressed to over 600 European academic institutions – aimed to map the level of activity around CSR education (teaching and research) in Europe. It analysed the extent of CSR education, the different ways in which it was defined and the levels at which it was taught. It considered drivers of CSR courses, particularly the historical role of motivated individuals and the anticipation of future success being dependent on more institutional drivers. Finally it considered main developments in CSR research both by business school faculty and PhD students, tomorrow's researchers and the resources devoted to CSR research.

Budget: € 9.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: September 2003 to February 2004

Lead Partner(s): EABIS & International Centre for CSR, Nottingham University Business School

Supporting Partner(s): The European Research Network for Business in Society, CSR Europe, The Copenhagen Centre and the European Foundation for Management Development

Internal Report(s): Inaugural EABIS Directory of institutional CSR profiles for European business schools. (www.eabis.org/directory)

Matten, D., Moon, J., Barlow, C. & Lo, K.Y.A. (2003). *Overview and Highlights: Data Analysis of Survey Results About CSR Teaching and Research in Europe*.

External Publication(s): Matten, D. & Moon, J. (2004). *Corporate Social Responsibility Education in Europe*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol.54 (4), pp.323-337

EABIS Research Project

Title: **The EABIS-EFMD 2nd European Survey on Business in Society Issues in Management Education**

Executive Summary: Building on its 2003 predecessor, again with the vital support of Nottingham Business School's ICCSR team, the "2nd

European Survey on Business in Society (BiS) and Corporate Responsibility (CR) Research, Education and Other Initiatives in Business Schools and Universities” aimed to map the current state of learning throughout Europe on these topics. The research component of this survey also contributed to the EU-sponsored “CSR Platform” Project.

The data and information gathered from this Survey were once again made publicly available in a searchable online Public Directory. The new Directory formed one of the pillars of the EABIS-EFMD “Gateway” Project – a new online knowledge portal intended to become Europe’s largest resource centre for corporate responsibility in research and education. Hereby the project addressed the growing demand for a single point of access and reference for those in need of more and better information, including corporate, academic, student, civil society and policy-making communities.

Budget: € 16.000

Funding Source: EABIS Corporate Funded Knowledge & Learning Programme

Period: June 2006 – June 2007

Lead Partner(s): EABIS & EFMD

Supporting Partner(s): International Centre for CSR, Nottingham University Business School

Internal Report(s): EABIS-EFMD Business in Society Gateway – Global Directory (www.businessinsociety.eu/directory)

Moon, J. (2008). *Trends in European CSR Education 2003 – 2007*

Orlitzky, M. & Moon, J. (2008). *Report on Second European Survey on Corporate Social Responsibility Research, Education and Other Initiatives in Business Schools and Universities.*

External Publication(s): N/A to date